

Effects Generated by Social Debt

Table 1: Sociotechnical factors Affected by Social Debt.

Id	Effect and Primary studies
Factor: Software Development Team	
EDST01	Impacts team dynamics, particularly in achieving objectives and making collective decisions [PS8, PS9].
EDST02	Creates isolated subgroups within the team, hindering collaboration [PS7, PS9, PS24, PS32, PS34].
EDST03	Decreases team morale [PS8, PS25, PS26].
EDST04	Reduces productivity and increases the amount of rework required [PS24, PS34].
EDST05	Leads to higher staff turnover [PS1, PS3, PS24, PS25, PS32].
EDST06	Causes conflicts among team members [PS1, PS2, PS34, PS36, PS42].
EDST07	Results in the absence of clear work standards [PS26, PS34].
EDST08	Fosters mistrust, irritation, and stress during social interactions [PS1, PS13, PS25, PS27, PS32, PS34, PS42, PS7].
EDST09	Creates difficulties in understanding relevant information [PS9, PS24, PS26, PS32].
EDST10	Weakens the sense of responsibility [PS2].
Factor: Project management	
EPM01	SD affects the overall understanding of the project, making it difficult to identify needs and complete planned activities [PS3, PS10, PS11, PS19, PS27, PS29].
EPM02	Slows down development and may contribute to project failure [PS3, PS9, PS11, PS19, PS29, PS32].
EPM03	Negatively impacts the management of large and complex projects [PS3, PS9, PS12, PS19, PS24, PS29, PS32].
EPM04	Leads to decision-making based on incomplete or fragmented information [PS3, PS10, PS12, PS19, PS29, PS32].
EPM05	Creates difficulties in managing responsibilities and coordinating efforts among team members [PS3, PS9, PS12, PS21, PS24, PS27, PS29, PS30].
EPM06	Results in poor task assignment and inadequate workload distribution [PS3, PS13, PS30, PS31, PS32].
EPM07	Causes flawed planning based on incorrect assumptions [PS3, PS10, PS13, PS19, PS24, PS31, PS33].
EPM08	Increases development time and overall project costs [PS3, PS9, PS11, PS19, PS24, PS29].
EPM09	Leads to delivery delays, affecting established timelines [PS3, PS9, PS13, PS19, PS29, PS32].
EPM10	Causes bottlenecks and task progress disruptions [PS3, PS9, PS13, PS19, PS29, PS38].
Factor: Technical quality of the software	
EQS01	Incompleteness and misinterpretation of requirements [PS10, PS26, PS40].
EQS02	Lack of understanding of stakeholders' needs, resulting in software that fails to meet customer expectations [PS10, PS24, PS26, PS39, PS43].
EQS03	Suboptimal modularization structures, complicating software maintenance [PS14, PS32].
EQS04	Use of inefficient or inappropriate code patterns [PS17, PS32, PS43].
EQS05	Poor programming practices that degrade code quality [PS10, PS17, PS32, PS43].

Id	Effect and Primary studies
EQS06	Faulty software components that hinder maintainability [PS10, PS43].
EQS07	Fragmented system architecture that obstructs a holistic view of the system [PS10, PS24, PS39].
EQS08	Late integration of components, increasing integration risk [PS10, PS39].
EQS09	Accumulation of technical debt [PS10, PS32, PS24, PS39, PS43].
EQS10	Increase in design smells, such as broken hierarchy, insufficient modularization, and cyclic dependencies [PS14, PS32].
Factor: Organizational culture	
EOC1	Creates internal divisions within the team [PS3, PS9, PS24, PS32, PS39].
EOC2	Undermines the effectiveness of leadership [PS1, PS10, PS25, PS26, PS39].
EOC3	Fosters perceptions of exclusion among members [PS9, PS25, PS27, PS39].
EOC4	Leads to disorganization and negatively impacts the work environment and team morale [PS3, PS19, PS10, PS25, PS32, PS43].
EOC5	An individualistic culture reduces collaboration, encourages isolation, and erodes shared values and norms [PS3, PS24, PS27, PS32].
EOC6	A weak organizational culture marked by a lack of shared values, leading to disorganized and inefficient structures [PS10, PS24, PS26, PS39].
EOC7	Cultural differences within the organization generate conflict, resistance to change, and the formation of cultural silos [PS9, PS24, PS26, PS27, PS39].
EOC8	Contributes to a negative and uncertain work environment [PS10, PS19, PS25, PS39].
EOC9	The Power Distance effect limits participatory decision-making, reinforces hierarchical imbalances, and promotes authoritarian cultures [PS9, PS25, PS27, PS39].
Factor: Personnel	
EPD01	Work overload generates personal pressure and high levels of stress [PS10, PS25, PS17, PS19, PS39, PS43].
EPD02	Lack of intrinsic motivation to engage with assigned tasks [PS1, PS19, PS25, PS32, PS43].
EPD03	Voluntary resignation or abandonment of the job [PS1, PS9, PS17, PS25].
EPD04	Feelings of underappreciation and professional frustration [PS10, PS17, PS19, PS25, PS43].
EPD05	Psychological strain and emotional distress [PS10, PS17, PS19, PS25, PS39, PS43].
EPD06	Manifestation of symptoms such as insomnia, anxiety, depression, frustration, and panic attacks [PS17, PS25, PS43].
EPD07	Social isolation within or outside the work environment [PS3, PS9, PS25, PS39].
EPD08	Physical and mental exhaustion, often accompanied by signs of chronic fatigue [PS10, PS25, PS17, PS39].
EPD09	Emotional problems leading to tense or conflictive interpersonal interactions [PS9, PS17, PS25, PS39].
EPD10	Loss of a sense of belonging to the team or organization [PS25, PS39].
EPD11	Gradual disinterest in work-related responsibilities [PS17, PS25, PS32].

Acronyms used: Factor Effect on Software Development Teams (EDST). Factor Effect on Project Management (EPM). Factor effect on Software Technical Quality (EPM). Factor effect on Software Quality (EQS). Factor effect on Organizational Culture (EOC). Factor effect on Personnel (EP).